

The Products of the Reaction between Hydrated Ferric Oxide and Perchloric Acid Mixed in Different Molar Proportions. Part I. Spectral Characterization of the Species Formed and Evaluation of the True Fe(III) Ion Hydrolysis

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Pure hydrated ferric oxide has been reacted with perchloric acid at $\sim 30^\circ$ by mixing them in different molar proportions. The molar ratio of Fe : HClO₄ required to stop forming colloidal solution is 1 : 1.5. The solutions have been subjected to hydrolysis at 1×10^{-4} M of Fe³⁺ and the hydroxo species formed have been spectrophotometrically characterized. The pH dependent distribution of the species Fe³⁺, Fe(OH)²⁺ and Fe(OH)⁺₂ has been described. The spectral characteristics of these species and their thiocyanato complexes have been given. The true hydrolysis constants of the reactions, Fe³⁺ \rightleftharpoons Fe(OH)²⁺, and Fe(OH)₂⁺ \rightleftharpoons Fe(OH)₂⁺ have been evaluated.

Dissolution of ferric oxide in perchloric acid gives rise to Fe(ClO₄)₃ salt. The hydrolysis of this compound produces several hydroxo species¹ depending on the experimental conditions. Though physicochemical studies on the hydroxo ferric species have been made²⁻⁵, detailed investigation on the nature of solutions arising by reacting hydrated ferric oxide with low and high concentrations of perchloric acid, has not been performed. In this study, a series of solutions have been prepared by treating the oxide with varied proportions of HClO₄. Small portions of these samples have been hydrolyzed at a very low iron concentration. Spectrophotometric study of all these samples have been made along with other physicochemical works, under varied experimental conditions, with a view to characterizing them.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals used were all of E. Merck (pro analysi) grade. Spectral measurements were taken in a Beckman DB apparatus using 1 cm thick silica cells. Solution pH was recorded with a Cambridge pH meter.

Preparation of solution: Thoroughly washed precipitate of hydrated ferric oxide (prepared by ammoniation of FeCl₃) was dialysed against conductivity water for over three weeks to make it practically ion free. The mass was filtered under suction and the adhered water was removed by warming at 60° in an oven for 2 hrs. This pure ferric hydroxide on analysis was found to contain 74.8% Fe₂O₃. Samples were prepared by reacting the hydrated ferric oxide with 1M perchloric acid in stoppered bottles (nos. 1-8) at $\sim 30^\circ$ for two weeks

with intermittent shaking. In this preparation, the amount of perchloric acid was kept constant, in each sample, only the iron content was varied to maintain different mole ratios. In all these samples a fraction of the hydrated ferric oxide was found to have settled down at the bottom unreacted. This part was filtered out and the filtrates were stored as stock samples. Each stock sample was analysed for the iron content and thereafter a portion was diluted with water to a concentration of $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ of Fe^{3+} and given two months time for hydrolysis*. Spectral and other measurements were then performed.

Ferric ammonium sulphate was prepared by oxidising ferrous ammonium sulphate with H_2O_2 . Ammonium thiocyanate solution prepared in double distilled water was estimated by titrating against standard $AgNO_3$ using eosin indicator.

Hydrolysis constant determination: It is known that the composition of the ferric thiocyanate complex depends on the concentration of the component, particularly that of the ligand. At a very low concentration, a 1 : 1 complex is known to be formed. It has been observed that, under identical conditions, the different hydrolysed ferric perchlorate samples prepared behaved differently towards SCN^- , as regards the colour intensity of the complex. Regarding this as the index of property difference of the existing ferric ion species, the optical densities of the formed complex was studied for determining the hydrolysis constant.

The concentration of the iron used was $1 \times 10^{-4} M$. The hydrolysis constant, K_{11}^h (equation 1) was studied using excess (100 folds) of NH_4SCN . This was done for restricting the complex formation into one species only. Complete complexing of iron was also another idea for getting extinction values directly from the $OD/[Fe]$ ratio. The samples used were 5*-8*. For a comparative study one of the samples contained ferric ammonium sulphate. For the other hydrolysis constant, \bar{K}_{11}^- (equation 2), sample number 4*, at different given acidities, was reacted with excess NH_4SCN .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The characteristics of the several ferric perchlorate samples are shown in Table 1. From these results curves of Fig. 1 have been constructed. The theoretical equivalent iron consumption curve, QC [on the basis of $Fe(ClO_4)_3$ salt] crosses the experimental iron dissolution curve, QB at D ($Fe : HClO_4$ as 2.5 : 3). When mixed in this ratio, dissolved iron would form the salt $Fe(ClO_4)_3$. Above this point, part of the excess iron would be colloiddally dispersed (hatched area BDC). Below this, some polymeric iron hydroxo species together with $Fe(ClO_4)_3$ are supposed to exist. Actually one yellow polymeric sample has been obtained (sample 3). The colourless samples resulted in the higher numbers are believed to be mixtures of $Fe(OH)(ClO_4)_2$, $Fe(ClO_4)_3$ and complexed iron perchlorate⁶. Formation of complexed iron perchlorate is anticipated since a part of the hydrated iron oxide remained unreacted at a $Fe : HClO_4$ ratio as high as 1 : 15. Therefore, down to DE zone species of the hydroxo iron complex, their monomer and polymers, and perchlorate complexed iron may exist as a mixture.

* Hydrolysed samples are marked with asterisks. Complete hydrolysis is assumed.

TABLE 1

Hydrated ferric oxide and perchloric acid reaction at ~ 30°

Samples	Mole ratio (Fe : HClO ₄)	Total Fe added (in gm.)	Fe in solution (in gm.)	Colour and state of solution	pH
1	4 : 3	3.64	1.31	Deep red, colloidal	0.77
2	3 : 3	2.73	1.04	„	0.65
3	2 : 3	1.82	0.73	Yellow, non-colloidal	0.58
4	1 : 3	0.91	0.40	Colourless	0.24
5	1 : 6	0.46	0.20	„	0.11
6	1 : 9	0.30	0.14	„	0.07
7	1 : 12	0.27	0.11	„	0.05
8	1 : 15	0.18	0.09	„	0.04

pH for samples 1–3 are experimental values. Due to high acidity, pH for samples 4–8 have been calculated on the basis of unreacted H⁺ ions in solution.

Considering equilibrium has been attained in the samples, the above non-equivalent nature of the acid reaction can be looked upon also in the light of the iron oxide association concept proposed by Parkes *et al*⁷. According to this view, until the solution is strongly acidic the surface hydroxyl groups have only access to be attacked by the acid, leaving the

Fig. 1. Perchloric acid digestion of hydrated ferric oxide. QC : theoretical iron consumption curve; QB : experimental iron consumption curve; QA : curve for non consumed iron; E : ratio of Fe (added)/Fe (consumed) curve; F : ratio of Fe (non consumed)/Fe (consumed) curve. For curves E and F ordinate is a pure number.

submerged iron molecules to remain free. Whatever might be the mechanism behind, from the unusual acid reaction observed at a pH nearly zero, the probable formation of perchlorate complexed iron cannot be ruled out. In Fig. 1, the unreacted iron mass (curve QA), the ratios of $Fe(\text{added})/Fe(\text{reacted})$, curve E, and $Fe(\text{unreacted})/Fe(\text{reacted})$, curve F, are also shown for a little elaboration of the facts.

At a fixed acidity the rate of hydrolysis of the ferric ion is dependent mainly upon the concentration and the temperature. For the iron concentration ($1 \times 10^{-4}M$) used in the present investigation, it took almost two months for the reaction to completion at $\sim 30^\circ$. In Fig. 2 the spectra of most of the samples are depicted. The points lodged with arrow heads refer to the corresponding samples OD at 300 nm immediately after dilution.

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of hydrolysed ferric perchlorate samples. Curve numbers correspond to sample numbers. Arrow heads indicate OD values at zero time after dilution. $\lambda_{max} = 240$ nm curve holds for all samples at $pH \leq 0$.

Samples 1* and 3* do not indicate any change telling the non-occurrence of any further reaction with time. An interesting feature of the curves are the appearance of absorption maximum at 240 nm for $1M$ and $> 1M$ acid diluted solutions of samples 1, 3, 5, 7 and 8 at $1 \times 10^{-4}M$ of Fe^{3+} and that at 300 nm for water diluted solutions of samples 5, 6 and 8 (pH 2.96 to 2.65) also at the same concentration of iron. Samples 1 and 3 diluted by water (*i.e.*, samples 1* and 3*) at their respective pH 4.15 and 3.65, do not show any maximum absorption point. Existence of different species in the samples can explain these spectral characteristics (240 nm, for Fe^{3+} species, 300 nm for $Fe(OH)^{2+}$ species, and no maximum absorption for $Fe(OH)^{+}_2$ species). The decrease in the heights of the absorption maximum from samples 5* to 8* indicates increase in the $Fe^{3+}/Fe(OH)^{2+}$ ratio in these samples. The existence of Fe^{3+} ion in high acid medium ($pH \leq 0$) has been believed^{4,5,8} to give λ_{max} at 240 nm. A few workers^{3,5} have demonstrated the maximum absorption around 300 nm for the $Fe(OH)^{2+}$ species. Though $Fe(OH)^{+}_2$ dimer has a λ_{max} at 335 nm, such a dimer characteristic⁵ is absent

in the present samples. The 240 nm band has been believed by some workers as due to the combined contribution of Fe^{3+} and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ species. However, accepting the obliteration effect³ of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$, a prominent 240 nm maximum most probably means only a trace of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ species (Fig. 2). In literature the hydroxo ferric species has been reported to be yellow in colour¹. In the present study only samples which have no absorption maximum and are believed to be $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{+}_2$ species are yellow in colour. Other samples are all colourless. When alkali is added externally to a colourless sample, it becomes yellow though its $p\text{H}$ is the same as that of another colourless sample. This observation also suggests that the method of preparation has much saying on the composition of the solution¹¹.

TABLE 2

First hydrolysis constant, K^{h}_{11} of Fe^{3+} ions

Samples	$p\text{H}$	$K^{h}_{11} \times 10^2$	Ave. K^{h}_{11}	$-\Delta G$ k.cal.
6*	2.77	1.214		
7*	2.69	1.036	1.110	2.73
8*	2.65	1.100		
$\text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$	2.00	1.090		

Only the samples diluted by 1M acid have been observed to obey Beer's law. Those diluted by water have been found not to obey this optical law satisfactorily. This proves that samples in 1M acid all contain Fe^{3+} species, and those diluted by water contain a mixture of different species. We like to put a note here that Stockmayer and Rabinowitch³ observed that the species $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ did not obey Beer's law.

Hydrolysis of Fe^{3+} ion can take place in different ways¹¹. The equilibria considered in the present study are the following :

It is only qualitatively known that the blood red colouration of the ferric thiocyanate complex is $p\text{H}$ dependent⁹. The samples of the present investigation, containing different species, behaved differently towards the SCN^- ligand. For a fixed high concentration of NH_4SCN , Fe^{3+} gave most intense colour, $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ gave less intense colour, and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{+}_2$ imparted no colour at all. This is not entirely due to the direct $p\text{H}$ effect, because freshly prepared ferric ammonium sulphate solution ($p\text{H} > 4.0$) gave an intense colour which was absent for sample 4* having mostly $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{+}_2$ species at a $p\text{H}$ 3.65. It is anticipated that introduction of -OH group into the Fe^{3+} ion probably eliminates the complexing characteristics with the SCN^- group. Unequal complexing behaviour of the ferric ion species with benzilic acid ligand has been observed by the authors¹².

The equilibrium,

in presence of excess NH_4SCN becomes,

This was investigated using samples 5*, 6*, 7* and 8* which contained Fe^{3+} and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ species in different proportions. A sample of the ferric ammonium sulphate in sulphuric acid was also employed for a comparative study. The other equilibrium,

in presence of NH_4SCN becomes,

This was studied using acidified samples of no. 4*. The minimum $p\text{H}$ was maintained above the $p\text{H}$ of the sample 5*, thus to enable only the existence of the $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ and the $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^+$ species.

Fig. 3. Absorption spectra of $\text{Fe}(\text{III})$ -thiocyanate complex at $0.70 \times 10^{-4} M$. 1 : sample 4* at $p\text{H} = 3.24$; 2 : sample 4* at $p\text{H} = 3.18$; 3 : sample 4* at $p\text{H} = 2.88$; 4 : sample 4* at $p\text{H} = 2.70$; 5 : sample 1* in $1M$ acid at $0.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ of Fe^{3+} at $\text{Fe} : \text{SCN}$ ratio of 1 : 2; 6 : sample 1* in $1M$ acid at $0.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ of Fe^{3+} at $\text{Fe} : \text{SCN}$ ratio of 1 : 1; 7 : sample 5* at $p\text{H} = 2.96$; 8 : sample 6* at $p\text{H} = 2.77$; 9 : sample 7* at $p\text{H} = 2.69$; 10 : sample 8* at $p\text{H} = 2.65$; 11 : ferric ammonium sulphate at $p\text{H} = 2.00$; 12 : samples 1* and 8* in $1M$ acid.

In Fig. 3 all the ferric thiocyanate spectra are shown. Numbers 1–4 represent thiocyanate spectra for the equilibrium 4. Using the extinction values at 470 nm, from the OD/conc. ratio, and considering the general extinction-concentration scheme¹⁰, the concentrations of the individual species were calculated and the hydrolysis constants found out (Table 3). For the equilibrium 3, curves 8–12 have been utilised. The maximum rise in OD (curve 12) has been observed for samples 1 and 8, both in 1M HClO₄. They yielded almost equal values inferring complete conversion of the hydroxo species into Fe³⁺ ion. One of the samples (curve 11) contained ferric ammonium sulphate. All the hydrolysis constants (Table 2) were calculated in the manner discussed above.

TABLE 3

<i>Second hydrolysis constant, $\bar{K}^{h_{11}}$ of Fe³⁺ ion</i>				
Samples	pH	$\bar{K}^{h_{11}} \times 10^2$	Ave. $K^{h_{11}} \times 10^2$	$-\Delta G$ k.cals.
4*	3.18	1.037		
4*	2.88	0.800	0.842	2.90
4*	2.70	0.688		

Looking into Table 4, a direct comparison between the earlier and the present findings of the hydrolysis constants can be readily made. The present values are greater than all those obtained earlier. The medium for all the samples though contained NH₄SCN as foreign electrolyte its concentration was equal and low (0.027 M) in all the samples. Milburn and Vosburgh⁴ inferred that ionic strength variation does not have much influence on the $K^{h_{11}}$

TABLE 4

Comparison of ferric ion hydrolysis constants

Author	$K^{h_{11}} \times 10^4$	$\bar{K}^{h_{11}} \times 10^4$
Hedstorm ²	9.0	—
Milburn & Vosburgh ⁴	67.0	—
Rabinowitch & Stockmayer ³	35.0	—
Bray & Hershey ¹³	60.0	—
Cotton & Wilkinson ¹	8.9	5.5
Lamb & Jacques ¹⁴	—	0.2
Richard & Sykes ¹⁵	66.0	—
Present Work	111.0	84.0

values though Stockmayer and Rabinowitch³ reported variation of $K^{h_{11}}$ on the specific composition of the solution. The wide variation of $K^{h_{11}}$ and $\bar{K}^{h_{11}}$ in the hands of different workers is thus interesting from the standpoint of experimental method as well as the specific composition of the salts used. In the present study the effect of the ionic strength or the

nature of the different salts has not been explored. Using the present hydrolysis constants a computation of the percentages of the Fe^{3+} , $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$ and $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$ species has been made for low and high $p\text{H}$ values. The values have been compared with those of Matijevic *et al.*¹¹ in Table 5. These authors used the hydrolysis constants of Hedstorm² for calculation. A disagreement is readily seen. For a 100% Fe^{3+} ion to exist their data correspond to a $p\text{H}$ around 1.5. The presently obtained value is 0. This is more reasonable because at around a $p\text{H} \leq 0$, Fe^{3+} ions mostly predominate^{4,5,8}. We can thus logically conclude that the present hydrolysis constants are more accurate and probably the true values. It can be added that for a 100% $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$ species occurrence Hedstorm's values correspond to a $p\text{H}$ 5.5 compared to a value 4.0 calculated basing on our hydrolysis constant values.

TABLE 5

Percentage compositions of ferric species at extreme pH

$p\text{H}$	Present Work			Matijevic <i>et al.</i> ¹¹		
	% Fe^{3+}	% $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$	% $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$	% Fe^{3+}	% $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})^{2+}$	% $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_2^+$
0	100	0	0	100	0	0
0.5	97	3	0	100	0	0
1.0	89	11	0	100	0	0
1.5	73	27	0	100	0	0
3.5	0	3	97	12	33	55
4.0	0	1	99	2	15	83
4.5	0	0	100	0	6	94
5.0	0	0	—	0	2	98
5.5	0	0	—	0	0	100

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